

Gamut of Histopathological Findings in Autopsy Specimens: Our Hospital Experience

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Abstract

Introduction: Histopathological examination of autopsy specimens is an indispensable tool for determining and correlating the cause and manner of death, and allows detailed study of a wide range of conditions, including infections, inflammations, tumors, and infrequent or unnoticed lesions. Recent advances in diagnostic medical technology have increased the use of non-invasive modalities, histopathological examination of autopsies remains the gold standard for obtaining direct morphological and histological diagnoses, and this study was therefore undertaken to investigate the gamut of histopathological findings in autopsy specimens at our institution

Objectives: The primary objective was to determine the range of histopathological lesions and identify any incidental findings.

Materials and Methods: This retrospective study included 1146 autopsy organs of which 760 organs showed significant changes archived over six years, from 2016 to 2021. Following ethical clearance, autopsy specimens sent for histopathological examination and diagnosis, irrespective of cause of death, were retrieved from the records. Hematoxylin and eosin-stained slides were retrieved and studied for histopathological details; inclusion criteria were all archived histopathological examination slides and records of autopsy specimens, and exclusion criteria were any records or slides that were not archived due to unavailability or loss; all data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Results: The study reveals that the heart was the most frequently examined organ (42.14%), with atherosclerosis being the most common pathology (25.98%). Incidental findings such as myxoma of the heart, fungal abscess and SCC metastatic deposits of the lung were also noted.

Conclusion: The findings underscore the continued importance of autopsy histopathology in elucidating disease processes and identifying unexpected pathologies, which have significant implications for understanding disease mechanisms and improving clinical practice.

Keywords: Autopsy, Histopathology, Organs, Heart, Atherosclerosis.

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Introduction

Histopathological examination of autopsy specimens remains a critical tool for establishing and linking the cause and manner of death.[1,2] Beyond this, it allows for the identification of a wide gamut of conditions, including infections, inflammatory processes, neoplasms, and other unexpected or uncommon lesions. [3,4] While advancements in non-invasive diagnostic techniques have gained prominence, the direct morphological and histological insights offered by autopsy histopathology continue to be the gold standard.[1-4] This study was therefore conducted to delineate the gamut of histopathological findings observed in autopsy specimens at our institution

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the spectrum of histopathological findings in autopsy specimens.
2. To analyze the frequency of different types of lesions and any incidental histopathological findings.

Material and Methods

This retrospective study included 1146 autopsy organs of which 760 organs showed significant changes archived over six years, from 2016 to 2021.

Following ethical clearance, autopsy specimens sent for histopathological examination and

diagnosis, irrespective of cause of death, were retrieved from the records of the Department of Pathology, Belgaum Institute of Medical Science, Belagavi. Hematoxylin and eosin-stained slides were retrieved and studied for histopathological details.

Inclusion Criteria: All archived histopathological examination slides and records of autopsy specimens.

Exclusion Criteria: Any records or slides that were not archived due to unavailability or loss.

Statistical Analysis: All data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Results are presented as percentages and illustrated in graphs and tables.

Results

Total 1146 autopsy organs were studied of which 760 organs showed significant histopathological changes. Of these, 26.1% were female and 73.9% were male. The most common age range was 20-40 years, accounting for 45.4% of cases (Chart 1).

Figure 1: Pie chart showing the age range distribution

Table 1: Distribution of Cases According to Organs Received

Organ	Number	Percentage
Heart	483	42.14
Lung	240	20.9
Kidney	104	9
Liver	65	5.6
Uterus cervix	61	5.3
Ovaries and fallopian tubes	50	4.3
Neck structures	43	3.7
Brain	35	3
Skin	28	2.4
Spleen	11	0.9
Stomach	7	0.6
Intestines	5	0.4
Autolyzed	14	1.2
Total	1146	100

Table 1 shows the distribution of 1146 received organs. The heart was the most common organ, representing 42.14% (483 cases), with the lung being the next most frequent at 20.9% (240 cases). Kidneys (9%, 104 cases) and liver (5.6%, 65 cases) were also notably represented. A group of organs, including the uterus cervix (5.3%), ovaries and

fallopian tubes (4.3%), neck structures (3.7%), and brain (3%), were received in smaller but still significant numbers. The skin, spleen, stomach, and intestines each constituted a minor fraction of the total. In 1.2% of cases (14 cases), the specimens were autolyzed and thus unidentifiable.

Table 2: Organs with significant Histopathological Findings

Organ Received	Histopathological Findings	Number of Organs with Significant Findings	Percentage
Heart	Atherosclerosis	184	25.98
	Old healed infarct	44	6.21
	Ventricular hypertrophy	26	3.67
	Myocardial infarction	13	1.83
	Myocarditis	2	0.28
	Other changes	57	8.05
Lung	Congestion	106	14.97
	Edema	89	12.57
	Tuberculosis	14	1.97
	Pneumonia	13	1.83
	Bronchopneumonia	10	1.41
	Lung abscess	3	0.42
	Other changes	28	3.95
Brain	Congestion	2	0.28
	Meningitis	1	0.14
	Pyogenic abscess	1	0.14
	Brain abscess	1	0.14
Kidney	Chronic pyelonephritis	22	3.10
	Acute tubular necrosis	10	1.41
	Calculus pyelonephritis	5	0.70
	Simple renal cyst	1	0.14
Spleen	CVC	3	0.42
	Congestion	1	0.14
Uterus cervix	Leiomyoma	1	0.14
	Decidual endometrium	1	0.14
	Postpartum changes	1	0.14
Ovaries and fallopian tube	Tubercular salpingitis	1	0.14
	Dermoid cyst-ovary	1	0.14
Liver	Fatty liver	21	2.96
	Congestion	12	1.69
	Cirrhosis	11	1.55
	Chronic hepatitis	1	0.14
Neck structures	Hyoid fracture	2	0.28
	Autolyzed	12	1.69
Stomach	Thinned out mucosa	1	0.14
	Autolyzed	2	0.28
Intestine	Thinned out mucosa	1	0.14
	Autolyzed	3	0.42
Skin	Snake bite	1	0.14
Organs	Total	708	100

Of 1146, 708 showed significant pathology in the organs. Histopathological examination of the most frequently involved organ, the heart, revealed a spectrum of findings, with atherosclerosis being the most prevalent (25.98%). Other significant cardiac pathologies included old healed infarcts (6.21%), ventricular hypertrophy (3.67%), myocardial infarction, and myocarditis. Calcifications involving the coronaries and valves, as well as pericarditis, were seen in 8.05% of cases (Table 2).

Isolated incidental findings in the heart were myxoma and anterior wall perforation (Table 3). In the lungs, pulmonary congestion (14.97%) and pulmonary edema were the most common histopathological features. Brain examination showed congestion, meningitis, and abscess. The kidneys most frequently presented with chronic pyelonephritis and acute tubular necrosis, while the liver commonly displayed fatty changes, congestion, and cirrhosis (Table 2).

Figure 1: Histopathology images a) Atherosclerosis with calcification, b) Myocardial infarction c) Lung with congestion and edema d) lung with caseous necrotising granulomatous lesion with inset showing Ziehl nelson highlighting the tubercular bacilli

Table 3: Incidental Findings in Organs Received

Organ	Incidental Finding	Number	Percentage
Heart	Myxoma	1	14.29%
Heart	Anterior wall perforation	1	14.29%
Lung	Fungal abscess	3	42.86%
Lung	SCC metastatic deposits	1	14.29%
Kidney	Tubular adenoma	1	14.29%
Total		7	100%

A few incidental histopathological findings were noted in various organs. The heart showed myxoma and anterior wall perforation. The lungs showed fungal abscess and metastatic deposits of squamous cell carcinoma. The kidney showed tubular adenoma (Table 3).

Figure 2: Incidental histopathology findings a) Myxoma of heart, b) Fungal abscess in lung c) Squamous cell carcinoma metastatic deposits in lung d) Tubular adenoma of kidney

Discussion

Autopsy examinations consistently provide essential knowledge regarding the underlying causes of death and disease, maintaining their crucial role in contemporary medicine. The histopathological analysis of autopsy tissues is an integral part of this process, enabling practitioners to meticulously describe the microscopic characteristics of a broad spectrum of diseases and conditions.[1-4] Notwithstanding developments in diagnostic technologies, the significance of histopathology derived from autopsies remains, offering a distinct and valuable opportunity for clinicians and researchers to achieve a more in-depth knowledge of disease mechanisms and their expressions.[5,6] The wide-ranging

histopathological findings encountered in autopsy specimens underscores the intricate and subtle details of disease diagnosis in the post-mortem setting.

Our study revealed the highest number of cases in the 21-30 year age group, predominantly among males. This finding aligns with other studies like Sarngal S et al.[6] and Adil et al.[7] also observed a higher occurrence in males, at 70.1% and 85.2% respectively. However, the peak age range in these prior studies (31-40 years) was a decade older than that observed in our cohort. Consistent with other autopsy-based research, our study identified a high prevalence of atherosclerosis in the heart (25.98%), mirroring rates reported by Sarngal et al.[6] (20.5%) and Adil et al.[7] (20.6%). Beyond

atherosclerosis, we also documented significant rates of old healed infarcts (6.21%) and ventricular hypertrophy (3.67%), suggesting a notable presence of chronic cardiac conditions in our cohort. Pulmonary congestion was the most common lung finding (14.97%), accompanied by edema (12.57%), tuberculosis (1.97%), and pneumonia (1.83%). The prominence of congestion and edema aligns with general trends observed in autopsy studies of lung pathology.[8]

Interestingly, the incidence of fatty liver in our series (2.96%) was relatively lower than reported in some other autopsy studies, [9,10] where it often features more prominently. Instead, we found other liver pathologies, such as congestion (1.69%) and cirrhosis (1.55%), to be more notable. Kidney pathology in our study was marked by chronic pyelonephritis (3.10%) and acute tubular necrosis (1.41%). The frequency of chronic pyelonephritis suggests a considerable presence of chronic kidney disease in our population, which is a significant health concern globally.[5-8]

Among less frequent findings, we identified hyoid fracture in neck structures (0.28%), a finding with forensic implications often explored in studies of traumatic deaths, and a case of tubercular

salpingitis in the ovaries and fallopian tubes (0.14%), a condition that, while uncommon, is recognized in the context of extrapulmonary tuberculosis.[11-13]

A comparative analysis of common histopathological findings across several studies, including the present study, is presented in Table 4. The table reveals both consistent and variable patterns. Atherosclerosis in the heart shows a relatively stable prevalence, ranging from 20.5% to 27.2%, with our study reporting 25.9%. Lung congestion exhibits more fluctuation across the studies, with a range of 12% to 27%, and our study's 14.9% within this range. The liver shows the most pronounced variation, particularly in fatty liver prevalence, which differs considerably from our 2.9% to Adil et al [7] 24%. Kidney tubular necrosis also demonstrates a wide range, from our 1.4% to Adil et al [7] 33%. Additionally, our study reports chronic pyelonephritis at 3.1%. These comparisons in Table 4 suggest that while some histopathological findings are relatively consistent, others show significant variability, potentially reflecting differences in the characteristics of the studied populations, the methodologies employed, or other influencing factors.

Table 4: Comparison of commonest Histopathological Findings in Autopsy Organs with other Studies

Organ with Histopathological change	Sarngal S et al [6]	Adil SA et al [7]	Patel et al [13]	Present Study
Heart-Atherosclerosis	20.5%	20.6%	27.2%	25.9%
Lung-Congestion	18%	12%	27%	14.9%
Liver-Fatty liver	10.2	24%	19.8	2.9%
Kidney-Tubular necrosis	7.3	33%	9.1%	1.4%
				Chronic pyelonephritis-3.1%

Incidental histopathological findings in autopsy specimens, though unexpected, can provide significant and valuable information about human disease, while simultaneously creating complexities in interpretation and reporting.[13,16-22] Our study revealed several interesting incidental findings, such as a fungal abscess of the lung, a cardiac myxoma, and metastatic squamous cell carcinoma deposits.

Table 5: Comparison of Interesting Incidental autopsy Findings in Various Studies

Study	Incidental Findings
Patel S et al [13]	Unsuspected neoplasia, Sickle cell anemia
Panchal MG et al [11]	Sickle cell anemia
Manjula K et al [16]	Acute lymphoblastic leukemia, Meningothelial meningioma
Subitha K [17]	Invasive mucormycosis stomach, Extra-renal rhabdoid tumor
Present Study	Myxoma of heart, Fungal infection of lung, SCC Metastatic deposits in lung

Table 5 presents a comparative overview of notable incidental histopathological findings across several autopsy studies, including our present Study. The spectrum of unexpected discoveries varies, encompassing conditions such as unsuspected neoplasia and sickle cell anemia [13], isolated sickle cell anemia [11], acute lymphoblastic leukemia and meningothelial meningioma [16], and

invasive mucormycosis of the stomach with an extra-renal rhabdoid tumor [17].

Our study identified a cardiac myxoma, a fungal infection of the lung, and metastatic deposits of squamous cell carcinoma as significant incidental findings. This compilation underscores the crucial role of autopsy in revealing unforeseen pathologies that may have remained undiagnosed during life.

The detection of such incidental findings is of paramount importance as it can contribute to a broader understanding of disease prevalence, unusual disease presentations, and the potential for co-morbidities. Furthermore, these unexpected discoveries can have implications for family history and genetic predispositions, highlighting the continued value of thorough post-mortem examinations in expanding our knowledge of human disease beyond clinical diagnoses.[18-22]

Conclusion

This study presents a holistic view of the histopathological findings encountered in autopsy samples at a tertiary care institution. The observed predominance of atherosclerosis and pulmonary congestion is in agreement with prior research. Notably, the discovery of incidental pathologies, including cardiac myxoma, fungal lung abscess, and metastatic squamous cell carcinoma, underscores the vital role of autopsy in identifying unexpected medical issues. These findings not only deepen our understanding of disease pathways but also firmly establish the enduring critical role of autopsy histopathology in the modern medical landscape.

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